

Manchester Journal of Transnational Islamic Law & Practice

About

The Manchester Journal of Transnational Islamic Law & Practice (formerly the Journal of Islamic State Practices in International Law) was founded in 2005. The Journal is independent of any State, school of fiqh or institutional affiliation and has a diverse and global editorial board. It is indexed on Scopus and available both in electronic and printed forms.

Aims of the Journal

The principal objectives of the Manchester Journal of Transnational Islamic Law & Practice (MJTILP) are to provide a vehicle for the consideration of transnational forms of Islamic law and practice. Transnationalism in Islamic law is taken broadly as communications and interactions linking Islamic thoughts, ideas, people, practices and institutions across nation-States and around the globe. In recent times, research in Islamic law has shaped narratives based on nation-States, demographics, diasporic communities, and ethnic origins instead of developing around a central core. Contemporary issues of Islamic law are increasingly linked to geographical locations and ethnic or parochial forms of religious beliefs and practices. Expressions like American, European, British, Asian, and Arab Islam have widely gained acceptance.

Despite the growing importance of dialogue to develop shared understandings of issues facing Islamic law and proposing coordinated solutions, the contemporary research and scholarship has not developed harmoniously and remains piecemeal and sporadic. Researchers and practitioners of Islamic law are drawn from a wide variety of subjects and come from various regions of the world but have insufficient institutional support for sharing information and comparing experiences. Innovation in various strands and paradigms of Islamic law and practice is stifled because there are limited spaces where evolutionary, collaborative and interdisciplinary discourses can take place. This in turn hampers the ability to build on past research and record best practices, negatively impacting a consistent and orderly development of the field. There is a need to constitute a world community of Islamic law scholars based on interactions and aspirations moving across linguistic, ethnic, geographical and political borders.

The MJTILP is inspired by the need to fill these gaps. It provides a platform to legal and interdisciplinary scholars and researchers for critical and constructive commentaries, engagements, and interactions on Islamic law and practice that are built upon configurations in contemporary contexts. It welcomes contributions that look comparatively at Islamic law and practice that apprise and inspire knowledge across national boundaries whether enforced by a State or voluntarily practiced by worldwide Muslim communities. We are equally interested in scholarships on encapsulated cultural worlds, diaspora, identity and citizenship that are embedded and circumscribed by religious ties. As it has been the practice of the journal since its establishment in 2005, it also has a specific interest in issues relating to the practice of Muslim States in international law, international law issues that may concern Muslim countries, and all aspects of law and practice affecting Muslims globally.

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The Principle of Non-refoulement as 'Urf in Muslim Societies

Malahayati Rahman*

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Abstract: This article analyses the principle of non-refoulement and its relationship with the concept of 'urf (customary law) in Muslim societies. Non-refoulement is a principle of international law that prohibits the expulsion or rejection of individuals who face a severe risk to their life, liberty, or dignity in their country of origin. Whereas 'urf is a concept that refers to social practices that are recognised and respected in Muslim societies. In the context of non-refoulement, the 'urf of Muslim communities shows the importance of safeguarding human rights and protecting individuals who face severe threats in their countries of origin. Through historical analysis and policy studies, this article explains how the principle of non-refoulement is inherently related to the values of 'urf in Muslim society. The analytical outcomes show that the principle of non-refoulement can be applied effectively in Muslim countries as 'urf that requires the protection of human rights and promotion of social inclusion for refugees and immigrants.

Keywords: Non-refoulement; Refugees; Muslim society; human rights; 'Urf

I. INTRODUCTION

The global refugee crisis and immigration challenges have become urgent issues today.¹ Millions of people have fled their homeland due to conflict, war, human rights violations, and deteriorating economic conditions.² In dealing with this situation, the principle of non-refoulement has become increasingly relevant and essential in safeguarding human rights and providing protection to those in need.³ The principle of non-refoulement is prohibiting or not

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¹ 'Global Trends' (UNHCR) <<https://www.unhcr.org/global-trends>> accessed 6 August 2023; 'Who Is a Refugee, a Migrant or an Asylum Seeker?' Amnesty International (n.d.) <<https://www.amnesty.org/en/what-we-do...>> accessed 6 August 2023; Human Rights Watch, *World Report 2022* (2021) <<https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2022>> accessed 6 August 2023.

² World Bank, *Forcibly Displaced: Toward a Development Approach Supporting Refugees, the Internally Displaced, and Their Hosts* (Washington, DC: World Bank 2017) <<http://hdl.handle.net/10986/25016>> accessed 6 August 2023.

³ 'Note on Non-Refoulement (Submitted by the High Commissioner)' UNHCR 1977) <<https://www.unhcr.org/publications/note-non-refoulement>> accessed 6 August 2023; United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, 'The Principle of Non-Refoulement as a Norm of Customary International Law.

allowing a country to return or send refugees to an area where they will face persecution or persecution that endangers their lives for reasons related to race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or because of his political beliefs.⁴ This principle stipulates that no country may return or send refugees or asylum-seekers to a region where their lives and safety are threatened unless their presence threatens the country's security. Article 33(1) of the 1951 Geneva Convention on Refugees states:

“No Contracting State shall expel or return (*refouler*) a refugee in any manner whatsoever to the frontiers of territories where his life or freedom would be threatened on account of his race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion.”

Article 33(1) creates the non-refoulement obligation by requiring no member country to repatriate or expel a person to a territory that could threaten his or her life and freedom simply because of his personal identity, beliefs or political views. Protection of human rights, especially torture and harsh, humiliating, and inhumane punishment, is intimately tied to non-refoulement.⁵ This principle is the basis for refugees and asylum seekers, institutionalised in numerous international and national legal instruments.⁶ Countries that signed the 1951 Refugee Convention and 1967 Protocol are immediately bound by it. Contracting parties must not extradite or repatriate a person to a country that endangers their life or safety.⁷

Reciprocally, Islamic teachings that protect life, liberty, and human dignity illustrate non-refoulement.⁸ Islamic teachings emphasise safeguarding human life, freedom, and dignity regardless of religion, race, or ethnicity.⁹ The principle of non-refoulement in international law is in line with several principles of Islamic law, namely:

1. The protection of life: Islamic law places life as the most precious thing.¹⁰ The Qur'an states that “killing one human being is the same as killing all humankind”.¹¹ Non-refoulement in Islam prohibits expelling people who are in danger in their home country;

Response to the Questions Posed to UNHCR by the Federal Constitutional Court of the Federal Republic of Germany in Cases 2 BvR 1938/93, 2 BvR 1953/93, 2 BvR 1954/93' *Refworld* (31 Jan 1994) <<https://www.refworld.org/docid/437b6db64.html>> accessed 6 August 2023.

⁴ Guy S. Goodwin-Gill and Jane McAdam, *The Refugee in International Law* (3rd edn, Oxford University Press 2007) 205.

⁵ Elihu Lauterpacht and Daniel Bethlehem, 'The Scope and Content of the Principle of Non-Refoulement: Opinion' in Erika Feller, Volker Turk and Frances Nicholson (eds), *Refugee Protection in International Law* (UNHCR 2003) 3.

⁶ 'The 1951 Refugee Convention' *UNHCR UK* (n.d.) <<https://www.unhcr.org/uk/about-unhcr/who-we-are/1951-refugee-convention>> accessed 6 August 2023.

⁷ United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, *Refugee Protection: A Guide to International Refugee Law* (2001) 11.

⁸ Irene Oh, *The Rights of God: Islam, Human Rights, and Comparative Ethics* (Georgetown University Press 2007) 12 <<https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt2tt56s>> accessed 6 August 2023.

⁹ Deviana Yuanitasari and Hazar Kusmayanti, 'Human Rights Thought: Between Islamic Law and The Universal Declaration of Human Rights' (2021) 1 *Asian Journal of Law and Humanity* 19, 25.

¹⁰ Moh Dahlan and others, 'The Islamic Principle of Hifz Al-Nafs (Protection of Life) and COVID-19 in Indonesia: A Case Study of Nurul Iman Mosque of Bengkulu City' (2021) 7 (7) *Heliyon* 1, 2.

¹¹ Qur'an, Al-Maidah (the Table) 5:32.

2. Freedom: Islam also emphasises the importance of individual freedom.¹² The Qur'an states that there is no compulsion in religion.¹³ Islamic law upholds freedom, so non-refoulement protects people from oppression and inhumane treatment at home and
3. Human dignity: Islamic law teaches the importance of respecting human dignity.¹⁴ All individuals have the right to be respected and recognised for their dignity.

In addition, the policies of Muslim societies regarding refugees and immigration are crucial factors to consider.¹⁵ By examining the practices and policies of Muslim societies, we can comprehend the challenges and opportunities associated with applying the principle of non-refoulement effectively and ensuring the protection of refugees and immigrants.

Understanding non-refoulement in Islamic law and its position in Muslim society is important to raise awareness of the obligation to protect human rights and the vulnerable in a religious and cultural environment. Against this background, this article analyses the principle of non-refoulement as an *'urf* (good habit) in Muslim societies, explores the relationship of the non-refoulement principle to Islamic religious values, and highlights the importance of implementing this principle in the policies of Muslim countries. We argue that the Muslim community not only considers non-refoulement as an *'urf*, but there is also significant convergence between international law and Islamic law on the principle of non-refoulement. Both legal frameworks prioritise the protection of individuals from harm and persecution, emphasising the sanctity of life, dignity, and freedom.

Based on the aforementioned problems, conducting theoretical, historical analysis, and policy studies on the principle of non-refoulement is appropriate. This article explains how the non-refoulement is inherently related to the values of *'urf* in Muslim society, theoretically and in policy practice. This research has employed the qualitative method to analyse secondary data sources, such as documents, books, and various scientific articles that address the issue. It has also reviewed existing practices to ensure discussions are founded on social reality.

The discussions in this article are structured as follows: Part II examines the non-refoulement principle according to international law and Islamic law; Part III defines *'urf* and its explanation through various examples and cases in Muslim society; and Part IV analyses the existence of non-refoulement as an *'urf*. This article concludes that non-refoulement is recognised as an *'urf* in the Muslim community, which, similar to the understanding of non-refoulement in international law, requires the protection of individuals from harm and persecution, emphasising the sanctity of life, dignity, and freedom. By strengthening the relationship between non-refoulement in international law and *'urf* in Islamic law, Muslim societies can create a more comprehensive and integrated framework to protect human rights, particularly in refugee situations.

¹² Khabirah Yahya, 'Islam, Individual Freedom, and the Pandemic: Reflections of a Muslim American Woman Living in the Middle East' (2020) 3 (1) Journal of Islamic Faith and Practice 107, 109.

¹³ Qur'an, Al-Baqarah (the Cow) 2:256.

¹⁴ Mohamed Bin Ali, 'Delineating the Concept of Human Dignity in the Qur'an: Karamah al-Insan as an Antidote to Religious Conflicts and Violence' (2022) 9 (1) Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal 220, 223.

¹⁵ Yvonne Jazz Rowa, 'Disruptive Islamism: "Islamic Radicalization" in Public Discourse, and the Strategies and Impact of Terrorist Communication on Refugees and Host Communities' (2023) 15 (1) Behavioral Sciences of Terrorism and Political Aggression 82, 89; S. Casey, 'G20 Policy Makers Should Support Wider Religious Roles in Refugee Resettlement' (2017) <<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/G20-policy-makers...>> accessed 7 August 2023.

II. THE CONCEPT OF NON-REFOULEMENT PRINCIPLE

In this section, we will explore the concept of non-refoulement principle comprehensively, shedding light on some key points and critical aspects of the non-refoulement principle and its significance within international and Islamic law.

A. Non-Refoulement Principle According to International Law

The term non-refoulement comes from the French word ‘*refouler*,’ which means to force back, expel, or reject. It refers to a fundamental concept of international refugee law that bans states from returning refugees to countries or territories where their lives or freedom may be threatened due to their race, religion, nationality, participation in a particular social group, or political opinion.¹⁶ The term refoulement is not the same as expulsion or deportation.¹⁷

In the early-mid 19th century, asylum and non-extradition applied only to political offences. Applying these principles in the current global landscape has become increasingly complex and relevant, particularly in light of ongoing conflicts, persecution, and humanitarian crises that force individuals to flee their home countries. Consequently, the interpretation and implementation of non-refoulement have evolved to address contemporary challenges, such as the displacement of people due to armed conflicts, environmental disasters, and other humanitarian emergencies. This evolution underscores the need for a comprehensive examination of the principle’s current situation and its implications for protecting the rights and safety of displaced individuals worldwide.

Non-refoulement is a crucial protection under international human rights, refugee, humanitarian, and customary law. It is considered a part of customary international law (*Jus Cogens*), binding on all states, whether or not they are parties to the Geneva Refugee Convention and Protocol. The non-refoulement principle is considered to form part of customary international law, based on consistent state practice and a recognition by states that the principle has a normative character. This recognition further solidifies the importance of the principle in international law and its acknowledgment in the 1951 Convention on the Status of Refugees.

Reflecting the international community’s commitment to preventing the return of refugees to a situation where their life or freedom would be at risk, Article 33 of the 1951 Convention on the Status of Refugees regulates the principle of non-refoulement, and its scope is as follows:

1. No Contracting State shall expel or return (*refouler*) a refugee in any manner whatsoever to the frontiers of territories where his life or freedom would be threatened on account of his race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion.
2. The benefit of the present provision may not, however, be claimed by a refugee whom there are reasonable grounds for regarding as a danger to the security of the country in which he is, or who, having been convicted by a final judgment of a particularly serious crime, constitutes a danger to the community of that country.

¹⁶ ‘Non-Refoulement’ <<https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration...>> accessed 7 August 2023.

¹⁷ Note on Non-Refoulement (n 3).

In summary, Article 33 of the 1951 Convention on the Status of Refugees establishes the fundamental principle of non-refoulement. It ensures that refugees are not sent back to situations where their life or freedom is at risk due to specific protected grounds, with limited exceptions for security and severe criminal concerns.

The principle of non-refoulement is not absolute and may be subject to exceptions in certain circumstances, such as when a person poses a threat to national security or public order.¹⁸ This exception is recognized in Article 33(2) of the 1951 Refugee Convention, which states that the principle of non-refoulement shall not apply to a refugee who is considered a danger to the security of the country or has been convicted of a particularly serious crime.¹⁹ The exception to non-refoulement based on national security and public order is often invoked by countries to justify their actions in denying or revoking refugee status and deporting individuals. This exception is a contentious issue, as it can potentially undermine the protection of refugees and lead to the violation of their human rights. India, as a signatory to the 1951 Refugee Convention, has incorporated the principle of non-refoulement into its domestic law. However, the country has also invoked the exception of national security and public order to deny refugee status and deport individuals, particularly in cases involving refugees from neighbouring countries such as Bangladesh and Myanmar.²⁰ The application of the exception to non-refoulement based on national security and public order can be complex and controversial. It requires a careful balance between protecting the rights of refugees and ensuring the security and well-being of the host country's population.²¹

Furthermore, the 1967 Protocol was born out of consideration of the development of the refugee situation and the limited scope of the 1951 Convention's application.²² The 1967 Protocol has no practical effect on interpreting the principle of non-refoulement, which applies across member states' territorial boundaries. The 1967 Protocol broadened the definition of refugees geographically and with time limits.²³

Apart from the 1951 Convention and the 1967 Protocol concerning the Status of Refugees, the principle of non-refoulement is also regulated in Article III (3) of the 1966 Principles Concerning the Treatment of Refugees,²⁴ which the Asian-African Legal Consultative Committee adopted. It also contains in Article 3 of the 1967 Declaration on Territorial Asylum,²⁵ which was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) as Resolution 2132 (XXII) on December 14, 1967. Article II (3) of the 1969 Organization of Africa Unity

¹⁸ Note on Non-Refoulement (n 3).

¹⁹ 'Non-Refoulement' <<https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration...>> accessed 7 August 2023.

²⁰ David Weissbrodt and Isabel Hortreiter, 'The Principle of Non-Refoulement: Article 3 of the Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment in Comparison with the Non-Refoulement Provisions of Other International Human Rights Treaties' (1999) 5 (1) Buffalo Human Rights Law Review 1, 25.

²¹ Note on Non-Refoulement (n 3).

²² United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, 'Colloquium on the Legal Aspects of Refugee Problems No. A/AC.96/INF.40', *Note by the High Commissioner* (1965).

²³ Paul Weis, 'The Development of Refugee Law' in Michigan Yearbook of International Legal Studies (ed), *Transnational Legal Problems of Refugees* (1982) <<https://www.unhcr.org/publications/colloquium...>> accessed 7 August 2023.

²⁴ United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, 'Bangkok Principles on the Status and Treatment of Refugees ("Bangkok Principles")' *Refworld* (31 December 1966) <<https://www.refworld.org/docid/3de5f2d52.html>> accessed 7 August 2023.

²⁵ 'Declaration on Territorial Asylum' Audiovisual Library of International Law (14 December 1967) <<https://legal.un.org/avl/ha/dta/dta.html>> accessed 7 August 2023.

Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa²⁶ and Article 22 (8) of the 1969 American Convention on Human Rights, Section III, paragraph 5 of the 1984 Cartagena Declaration also regulate the principle. Article 3 of the 1984 Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman, or Degrading Treatment or Punishment,²⁷ Article 7 of the 1966 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights,²⁸ and Article 3 of the 1950 European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms²⁹ apply the non-refoulement principle.

The International Convention for the Protection of All Persons from Enforced Disappearance, adopted on December 23, 2010, also includes provisions that prohibit the expulsion of a person by a state party where they would be subjected to enforced disappearance (Article 16). Moreover, according to Principle 5 of the UN Principles on the Effective Prevention and Investigation of Extra-Legal Arbitrary and Summary Executions, no one may be exiled against his or her will to a location where he or she may be subjected to extra-legal, arbitrary, or summary execution.

B. The Principle of Non-Refoulement According to Islamic Law

1. A Brief History

Pre-Islamic Arab culture had customs and practices that protected people who were forcibly displaced. While these practices were not explicitly termed non-refoulement, they demonstrated a recognition of the importance of providing refuge and protection to those in need.

Islamic history recognises the *Hajj* (pilgrimage) events, marked by the *tawaf* ritual performed around the *Kaaba* and by the presence of *Hajarul Aswad* (black stone), which stands for the protection of anyone entering the area.³⁰ The term *haram* (forbidden) attached to the City of Mecca is one of the world's first symbols of protection or asylum.³¹ Prophet Ibrahim mentioned the *Kaaba* as a place of refuge for asylum seekers, as mentioned in the Qur'an, which means:³²

“And (remember) when Abraham said: O my Lord, make this land (Mecca) a safe country, and keep me and my children and grandchildren away from worshipping idols.”

Based on this story, everyone who has received protection in the forbidden land (Mecca) has received guarantees from any actions or threats of harm that will injure his freedom. Anyone

²⁶ ‘OAU Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa - African Union’ (n.d.) <<https://au.int/en/treaties/oau-convention-governing-specific-aspects-refugee-problems-africa>> accessed 7 August 2023.

²⁷ ‘Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment’, *OHCHR* (n.d.) <<https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments...>> accessed 7 August 2023.

²⁸ ‘International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights’, *OHCHR* (n.d.) <<https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms...>> accessed 7 August 2023.

²⁹ ‘The Convention in 1950 - The European Convention on Human Rights.’ (n.d.) (*The European Convention on Human Rights*) <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/human-rights-convention/the-convention-in-1950>> accessed 7 August 2023.

³⁰ Ghassan Maarouf Arnaout, *Asylum in the Arab-Islamic Tradition* (Geneva: UNHCR 1987) 11.

³¹ ‘Chapter 48: The Conquest of Makkah’ (27 December 2012) <<https://www.al-islam.org/message-jafar-subhani/chapter-48-conquest-makkah>> accessed 6 August 2023.

³² Qur'an, Ibrahim (Abraham) 14:35.

who violates this protection will be subject to severe sanctions and considered to have betrayed his religion.³³ This concept of protection and sanctuary aligns with the Islamic vision of *hijrah*, which refers to the migration or journey of the Prophet Muhammad and his followers from Mecca to Medina. The word *hijrah* comes from *hajara*, which means to decide, leave, separate, walk, rush, or move.³⁴ Meanwhile, according to scholars, *hijrah* means leaving the land of the infidels (*Darul Kuffar*) to the land of peace or Islam (*Darul Islam*).³⁵ The Prophet left the city of Mecca for Medina because of pressure and oppression against himself and his followers, so he had to save his believers towards a better and independent life. *Hijrah* also means abandoning all interests, sacrificing wealth, and saving lives because Muslims' blood was made lawful, and their rights were taken away.³⁶ *Hijrah* also describes a future journey full of uncertainty. People who do *hijrah* are called *muhâjirîn* (refugees).

The incident at Hudaibiyah and the subsequent peace treaty between the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) and the Quraysh tribe of Mecca serve as a historical example of how Islam promotes the principles of refugee protection and non-refoulement.³⁷ The main points of the Treaty of Hudaibiyah included a 10-year truce between the two parties, the return of any Muslim who fled to Muhammad from the Quraysh without the permission of his guardian, and the non-refoulement of any individual who came to the Quraysh from the Muslims. Abu Jandal and his brother Abdullah were early converts to Islam, following the lead of their brother Abdullah ibn Suhayl. Due to their father's position in the leadership of Quraysh, they were persecuted and had to hide their conversion. The Prophet's actions during this event demonstrated his commitment to peace, diplomacy, and the protection of individuals seeking refuge, regardless of their background or beliefs.

One of the similarities between Islamic law and modern international law regarding handling refugees is the prohibition on returning refugees to countries or regions where the refugees will face the risk of persecution or persecution. In Islamic law, refugee protection is based on the concept of *amân*, meaning protection or safety.³⁸ Islam strictly forbids repatriating or returning refugees to a region where they fear losing their souls, freedom, and other fundamental rights.³⁹ Historically, Islam was the first religion to recognise the prohibitions on the repatriation and extradition of political criminals.⁴⁰

³³ Mukhlis, *Pengaturan Perlindungan Hukum Terhadap Pengungsi Lintas Batas Negara Menurut Hukum Internasional dan Hukum Islam* (in Bahasa Indonesia) [Arrangements for Legal Protection of Refugees Against National Borders According to International Law and Islamic Law] (Padang: Universitas Andalas 2016) 6.

³⁴ Ahmad Warson Munawwir, *Al-Munawwir Kamus Arab-Indonesia* (in Bahasa Indonesia) [*Al-Munawwir Arabic-Indonesian Dictionary*] 14th edn (Surabaya: Penerbit Pustaka Progresif 1997) 505.

³⁵ Ahsami Sami'un Jazuli, *Hijrah Dalam Pandangan Alqur'an* (in Bahasa Indonesia) [*Hijrah in the View of the Qur'an*] Eko Yulianti edn (I) (Jakarta: Gema Insani Press 2006) 12.

³⁶ Shafiyurrahman Al-Mubarakfuri, *Ar-Rahiq Al-Makhtum: Sirah Nabawiyah Biografi Rasulullah S.A.W. Terlengkap dan Terotentik* (in Bahasa Indonesia) [*Ar-Rahiq Al-Makhtum: Sirah Nabawiyah Biography of Rasulullah S.A.W. Complete and Authentic*] Faris Khairul Anam and Sujilah Ayu (eds) (Jakarta: Qisthi Press 2014) 193-194.

³⁷ Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. 'Pact of Al-Hudaybiyah' Encyclopedia Britannica (1998) <<https://www.britannica.com/event/Pact-of-Al-Hudaybiyah>> Accessed 26 September 2023.

³⁸ Ahmad Al-Dawoody and Tilman Rodenhäuser, 'The Principle of Non-Refoulement under Islamic Law and International Law: Complementing International Legal Protection in Muslim Contexts' (2021) <<https://blogs.icrc.org/law-and-policy/2021/06/20/non-refoulement-islamic-law>> accessed 26 September 2023.

³⁹ Muhammad Alvi Syahrin, 'Perlindungan Terhadap Pencari Suaka dan Pengungsi Menurut Hukum Internasional (Studi Filosofis dan Ontologis Keilmuan)' (in Bahasa Indonesia) ['Protection of Asylum Seekers and Refugees According to International Law (Scientific Philosophical and Ontological Studies)'] (2019) 19 (1) Nurani: Jurnal Kajian Syari'ah dan Masyarakat 63, 64.

⁴⁰ Sobhi Rajab Mahmassani, *The Principles of International Law in the Light of Islamic Doctrine* (Leiden: the Hague Academy of International Law 1967) 24.

2. *Maqasid-e-Shariah*

Islam views humans as equal, regardless of skin colour, religion, race, class, nation, or wealth.⁴¹ The historical event of the *hijrah*, which marked the migration of Prophet Muhammad and his followers from Mecca to Medina, exemplifies the pursuit of a haven to safeguard religious freedom and escape persecution. This concept of seeking sanctuary aligns with the Islamic jurisprudential concept known as *maqasid-e-shariah* (the objectives of Islamic law). It emphasises the protection of essential objectives, namely: (1) Preserving religion, (2) Preserving the Soul, (3) Preserving the Intellect, (4) Preserving the Offspring, and (5) Preserving the Property.⁴²

a. The Right to Preserving Religion

Maqasid-e-Shariah stipulate that the Muslim community must maintain religion, soul, mind, lineage, and property.⁴³ In some instances, the implementation of the duty to maintain one's faith includes prohibiting the return of refugees to regions where religious freedom is at risk.⁴⁴ Religion, the law of Allah, is essential for ensuring justice, equality, and protection from apostasy and worldly desires.⁴⁵

b. The Right to Preserving the Soul

The right to life is the most significant in Islam because it is sanctified, and its glory cannot be diminished because people are God's creation. Qur'an revealed that:⁴⁶

“(That is) the act of Allah who firmly makes everything; verily Allah is Aware of what you do.”

A Hadith narrated by Bukhari conveyed that:⁴⁷

“Rasulullah said: help your brother who persecutes or who is persecuted. O Messenger of Allah, I will help someone persecuted; what do you think if someone does tyranny? How can I help him? Rasulullah said: prevent him from doing injustice, then that is how you help him.”

⁴¹ M. Ahmadinejad and Yaser Aminroaya, 'Women's Right to Equal Recognition with Men from the Perspective of the International System of Human Rights and Islam' (2020) 11 (2) Comparative Law Review 1, 10.

⁴² Agus Nilmada Azmi, 'Islamic Humanitarian Principles and Migration: Reconstruction of Forced Migrant in Islam' (2022) 19 (1) Al-A'raf: Jurnal Pemikiran Islam dan Filsafat 111, 123.

⁴³ Zaenuddin Mansyur, 'Pembaruan Masalahah Dalam Maqāṣid Al- Sharī'ah: Telaah Humanistik Tentang *Al-Kulliyāt Al-Khamsah*' (in Bahasa Indonesia) ['Renewal of *Maslahah* in *Maqāṣid Al-Shariah*: A Humanistic Study of *Al-Kulliyāt Al-Khamsah*'] (2012) 16 (1) Ulumuna 71, 76.

⁴⁴ Anthin Lathifah and others, 'The Construction of Religious Freedom in Indonesian Legislation: A Perspective of Maqāṣid Hifz Al-Dīn' (2022) 6 (1) Samarah: Jurnal Hukum Keluarga dan Hukum Islam 369, 372.

⁴⁵ Zamakhsyari, *Teori-Teori Hukum Islam Dalam Fiqh dan Ushul Fiqh* (in Bahasa Indonesia) [*Theories of Islamic Law in Fiqh and Ushul Fiqh*] (Bandung: Citapustaka Media Perintis 2013) 99.

⁴⁶ Qur'an, An-Naml (the Ant) 27:88.

⁴⁷ Sahih al-Bukhari, vol 3, book 43, hadith 624.

In terms of preserving the soul, what becomes an element of *dharuriyyah* (primary necessity) is protecting human life so that he or she does not die.⁴⁸ The person must live because humans cannot exist without life. Humans also do not just want to live but also to live physically and spiritually.⁴⁹ The most basic principle in the prohibition of repatriation is the obligation to take care of the soul. Because it threatens a person's ability to maintain their soul, maintaining their soul is a *dharuriyyah*.⁵⁰

c. The Right to Preserving the Intellect

Intelligence is another obligation that must be maintained. In cases where refugees are forced to flee their country of origin due to threats to their freedom of thought and expression, the obligation to protect human intelligence applies.⁵¹ In addition to the five senses and revelation, intelligence is a means by which a person can acquire knowledge.

d. The Right to Preserving the Offspring

This right emphasises protecting and preserving human life, particularly the well-being and welfare of one's children or descendants.⁵² It is based on the understanding that children are a source of continuity for the family and society. Preserving the offspring involves ensuring their physical, emotional, and spiritual well-being and providing them with a safe and nurturing environment to grow and develop. In Islamic teachings, this right extends to various aspects of child-rearing, including education, healthcare, moral and ethical upbringing, and financial support. It underscores the importance of safeguarding the future generation's rights and interests, as they play a crucial role in the continuity of the family and the broader community.

e. The Right to Preserving Property

The right to preserve property focuses on protecting and maintaining one's wealth, assets, and property rights. It emphasises the importance of economic stability, financial security, and the responsible use of resources. In Islam, the right to private property is recognised and protected but comes with specific ethical and legal responsibilities. This right encourages individuals to acquire and manage wealth lawfully and ethically, avoid wastefulness and extravagance, and engage in charity and financial support for those in need. It also promotes fairness and justice in economic transactions and prohibits theft, fraud, and unjust exploitation of others' property.

The main principles in granting asylum and procedures for handling refugees are contained in the Qur'an, which means:⁵³

⁴⁸ Yulies Tiena Masriani, 'Sinergi Maqashid Syariah Asy-Syatibi Dengan Pancasila Sebagai Falsafah Negara Indonesia' (in Bahasa Indonesia) ['The Synergy of Maqasid *Shariah Asy-Syatibi* with Pancasila as the Philosophy of the Indonesian State'] (2023) 8 (1) *Jurnal Ius Constituendum* 19, 22.

⁴⁹ Ahmad Kosasi, *HAM Dalam Perspektif Islam* (in Bahasa Indonesia) [*Human Rights in Islamic Perspective*] (Jakarta: Salemba Dinia 2003) 17.

⁵⁰ Wahbah Az-Zuhaili, *Fiqh Islam Wa Adillatuhu* (in Arabic) [*Islamic jurisprudence and its evidence*] 1st edn (Jakarta: Gema Insani Pers 2011) 54.

⁵¹ Khairul Hamim, 'Ḥifz Al-Lisān as Maqāṣid Al-Sharī'ah Al-Ḍarūriyyah (Its Importance and Relevance in the Contemporary Era)' (in Arabic & English) ['Taking care of the way to speak as fundamental rights (Its Importance and Relevance in the Contemporary Era)'] (2021) 5 (1) *Samarah: Jurnal Hukum Keluarga dan Hukum Islam* 317, 322.

⁵² Agus Purnomo and others, 'Dimensions of Maqāṣid Al-Sharī'ah and Human Rights in the Constitutional Court's Decision on Marriage Age Difference in Indonesia' (2023) 7 (3) *Samarah: Jurnal Hukum Keluarga dan Hukum Islam* 1397, 1400.

⁵³ Qur'an, Al-Hasyr (the Exile) 59:9.

“And those who have occupied the city of Medina and have believed (*ansâr*) before (the arrival of) them (*muhâjirîn*), they (*ansâr*) love those who migrated to them (*muhâjirîn*). And they (*ansâr*) have no desire in their hearts for anything that is given to them (*muhâjirîn*), and they prioritise (the emigrants) over themselves, even if they are in trouble. And those who are protected from miserliness are the lucky ones.”

Based on the verse above, Ahmad Abu al-Wafa explains the principles of dealing with refugees and granting them asylum as follows:⁵⁴

1. Muslims must be happy and excited to welcome and get along well with refugees. Therefore, asylum seekers may not be expelled outside the territorial boundaries of the Islamic State or denied entry.
2. The Islamic Ummah must treat them well and prioritise their needs in life. They are prioritising other people in worldly affairs and prioritising *ukhrawi* (hereafter) issues.
3. Sympathetic acceptance of refugees without discriminating.
4. It is not permissible to refuse refugees even though the local population is experiencing a crisis, poverty, and increasing living needs.

The Qur'an has several guidelines on justice, especially in forming a just society, explaining the scope of justice in the relationship between human persons towards people with low incomes and those in need, as well as the relationship between the community and the nation.⁵⁵ In Islamic law's rules, it is clear that something recognised as '*urf*' is equivalent to a rule or something agreed upon (*al-ma'ruf' urf-an ka al-masyrut syart'an*).⁵⁶ This principle emphasises the importance of acknowledging and respecting customary practices or agreements in the context of Islamic law. The principle highlights the importance of recognising and respecting customary practices and local agreements ('*urf*') within the framework of Islamic law. It acknowledges that what is considered just and equitable can be influenced by the customs and traditions of a particular community and should be considered when making legal judgments or decisions. This concept helps ensure that Islamic law remains relevant and adaptable to diverse social and cultural contexts.

Likewise, something based on habit is equivalent to something written in the text or based on *shariah* text (*al-tsabit bi al-'urf ka al-tsabit bi an-nass*). This principle underscores the significance of established customs and practices ('*urf*') and their legal validity in the absence of explicit textual guidance (*nass*) in Islamic sources such as the Qur'an and Hadith. The principle helps balance the preservation of Islamic legal principles with the recognition of customary practices. It ensures that the legal system remains relevant and accessible to diverse communities while still upholding the core values and objectives of Islamic law.

⁵⁴ Ahmad Abu al-Wafa, *Hak-Hak Pencarian Suaka Dalam Syariat Islam Dan Hukum Internasional (Suatu Kajian Perbandingan)* (in Bahasa Indonesia) [*Rights of Seeking Asylum in Islamic Shari'a and International Law (A Comparative Study)*] Asmawi and others (eds) 1st edn (Riyadh: UNHCR Indonesia & Fakultas Syariah dan Hukum UIN Syarif Hidayatullah 2011) 23.

⁵⁵ Islamic Relief Worldwide, 'Islam and Refugees' *High Commissioner's Dialogue on Protection Challenges: Faith and Protection* (2012) <<https://www.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/legacy-pdf/50ab90399.pdf>> accessed 6 August 2023.

⁵⁶ Abu al-Wafa (n 54) 24.

3. *The Framework of the Principle of Non-Refoulement in Muslim Societies*

According to Islamic law, public authorities or regular citizens may grant asylum. It is based on the Hadith narrated by Imam Ahmad:⁵⁷

“The Believers (Muslims) are equal. The lowest can move on guarantees of protection, and they are hands (protecting) over people besides them.”

The state has the exclusive authority to regulate international affairs under Islamic law. It stipulates that: “Each of you is a leader and is responsible for what he leads. A priest is a leader and is responsible for what he leads.”⁵⁸ It means that only state administrators have the right to regulate domestic and foreign affairs. However, the right to asylum is an exception to this principle, as ordinary individuals can grant asylum.

According to Islamic law, the term *haqq al jihar* (neighborhood rights) is also an extension of the meaning of refugee. *Haqq al jihar* is a request for help to someone who confirms that a community leader can declare freely to provide protection or asylum to someone.⁵⁹ The concept of *haqq al jihar* was a legal concept of the *Jahiliyah* (ignorance), but after the arrival of Islam, this concept was still accepted and maintained in Arab society. In this concept, there are two parties: *mustajir*, who seek protection, and *mujir*, who provide protection. The *mustajir* must find a person who can protect himself (*mujir*) and enter into an agreement between the two that is announced to the public so that the *mujir* is responsible for protecting the *mustajir* and himself and his own family.⁶⁰ Hence, a Muslim can grant asylum or protection to people who seek protection from him without state interference.

Another note in the concept of granting asylum according to Islam is the territorial area. The granting of asylum in Islamic territories has the effect that refugees can enjoy this right in every region of an Islamic country because the country’s system is essentially one, and the territory of an Islamic country is also one, where this principle has begun to be applied in the European Union. Treaty establishing the European Community (consolidated version) - D. Protocols annexed to the Treaty establishing the European Community - Protocol (No 29) on asylum for nationals of Member States of the European Union (1997) states that European community agreements create a space without internal boundaries and give all residents within the union the right to move freely and live in the territory of member states.⁶¹ The UNHCR Program Executive Committee found that several 1951 Convention provisions allow a refugee living in a state party to exercise certain rights as a refugee in another state party without repeating the refugee status determination process.⁶²

⁵⁷ ‘Sunan Abi Dawud 2532 - Jihad (Kitab Al-Jihad) - Sayings and Teachings of Prophet Muhammad’ (n.d.) <<https://sunnah.com/abudawud:2532>> accessed 6 August 2023.

⁵⁸ K Elmadmad, ‘Asylum in Islam and in Modern Refugee Law’ (2008) 27 (2) Refugee Survey Quarterly 51, 53.

⁵⁹ Roziyah Sidik, Genius Muhammad Bin Abdullah: Mengungkap Kepakaran Nabi Dalam Pelbagai Dimensi Hidup (in Malay) [Genius Muhammad Bin Abdullah: Revealing the Prophet’s Expertise in Various Dimensions of Life] (Selangor: PTS Islamika 2004) 49.

⁶⁰ Abu al-Wafa (n 54) 85.

⁶¹ ‘EUR-Lex - 12006E/PRO/29 - EN - EUR-Lex’ (29 December 2006) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/treaty/tec_2006/pro_29/oj> accessed 6 August 2023.

⁶² UNHCR, ‘Conclusion Adopted by the Executive Committee on the International Protection of Refugees’ (2009) 65.

The concept of refugee protection became an essential part of the development of Islam when the Prophet Mohammad (Peace be Upon Him) had to emigrate to Medina from Mecca.⁶³ This *hijrah* became a symbol of the movement of Muslims from areas full of oppression to safe and peaceful areas. The treatment the Prophet received from the people of Medina during migration became a model for refugee protection in Islam.⁶⁴ This is reflected in the points of the Second *Aqabah Bai'at*, which were spoken as a pledge to protect the Prophet from the Quraysh threat.

Islam requires the receiving community (*the ansâr*) to be generous in accepting asylum seekers (*muhâjirîn* or *musta'min*) because this act is rewarding. Islamic law emphasises receiving and protecting people facing persecution and maintaining the sanctity of certain places. Anyone who seeks refuge in a mosque or the house of the Prophet's friends will be guaranteed safety and security.⁶⁵ However, Islam does not limit shelters only to houses of worship, but can also be given shelter in their homes or places specially made to accommodate refugees under the auspices of Islam, without discrimination between the poor and the rich, enslaved people or free people, Muslims, and non-Muslims.⁶⁶ Islamic law also recommends giving priority to the elderly, women, and children while in evacuation because they are considered to be more vulnerable and weak, as mentioned in the Qur'an.⁶⁷

Islamic law instructs its ummah to help and protect those who are weak and offers several ways to protect and support them.⁶⁸ In the Qur'an Allah explains as mentioned below:⁶⁹

“The former, first, from the *muhâjirîn* and *ansâr* groups and those who followed them well, Allah is pleased with them, and they are also pleased with Allah. God has prepared for them heavens flowing rivers in them forever. They live in it. That is a big win.”

The story of the re-occupation of Mecca by Muslims and Hind bint Utba, the wife of Abu Sufyan ibn Harb, is a significant event in Islamic history that relates to the principles of refugee protection and customs in Islam.⁷⁰ One of the remarkable aspects of the re-occupation of Mecca was the forgiveness extended by Prophet Mohammed to his enemies, including Hind bint Utba, who had conspired to kill his beloved uncle Hamzah at the Battle of Uhud. Despite her past actions, Prophet Mohammed forgave Hind, and she eventually embraced Islam. The story of the Mecca Conquest and Hind bint Utba exemplifies the principles of protection, mercy, and forgiveness in Islam. It demonstrates how even those who were once enemies of the Prophet Muhammad and his followers could find refuge, forgiveness, and the opportunity for redemption within the Islamic community.

⁶³ Arafat Madi Shoukri, 'Refugee Status in Islam: Concepts of Protection in Islamic Tradition and International Law' (2011) 24 (3) *Journal of Refugee Studies* 629, 632.

⁶⁴ Fajar Fajar, 'Praxis Politik Nabi Muhammad SAW (Sebuah Tinjauan Teori Politik Modern dan Ketatanegaraan)' (in Bahasa Indonesia) ['The Political Praxis of the Prophet Muhammad SAW (An Overview of Modern Political Theory and State Administration)'] (2019) 4 (1) *Al-Adalah: Jurnal Hukum dan Politik Islam* 82, 91.

⁶⁵ *Al-Mubarakfuri* (n 36) 209.

⁶⁶ *Islamic Relief Worldwide* (n 55).

⁶⁷ Qur'an, An-Nisaa (the Women) 4: 2, 9, 36, 75, 98, 127.

⁶⁸ *Mukhlis* (n 33) 8.

⁶⁹ Qur'an, At-Taubah (the Repentance) 9:100.

⁷⁰ Muslim Hands, 'Lessons we can learn from the Conquest of Makkah (Fath Makkah)' (2023) <<https://muslimhands.org.uk/latest/2023/04/summary-and-importance-of-conquest-of-makkah>> accessed 26 September 2023.

In the modern world, Article IX of the Universal Islamic Declaration of Human Rights, established by the Islamic Council in London in 1981, states:⁷¹

1. Every persecuted or oppressed person has the right to seek refuge and asylum. This right is guaranteed to every human being irrespective of race, religion, colour and sex.
2. *Al Masjid Al Haram* (the sacred house of Allah) in Mecca is a sanctuary for all Muslims.

The Organization of the Islamic Conference (O.I.C.), as a representative of Islamic countries, emphasises refugees in Article 12 of the 1990 Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Cairo Charter), which states:⁷²

“Every man shall have the right, within the framework of *Shariah* (Islamic law), to free movement and to select his place of residence whether inside or outside his country and if persecuted, is entitled to seek asylum in another country. The country of refuge shall ensure his protection until he reaches safety unless asylum is motivated by an act which *Shariah* regards as a crime.”

According to Islamic law, anyone may seek and be granted asylum in a Muslim nation. Muslim nations are obligated to accept and protect refugees in times of need, especially the government.⁷³ Compared to other modern refugee laws, the *hijrah* provides a broader understanding of refugees and gives individuals the right to grant asylum rather than the state.⁷⁴

Hijrah, in the view of Islam, is divided into two, namely *hijrah ma'nawiyah* and *makkaniyah*. *Hijrah ma'nawiyah* is an obligatory spiritual migration and must be carried out by all Muslims in the form of a transfer of morals and behaviours toward a better direction.⁷⁵ In comparison, *hijrah makkaniyah* is a physical movement from a wrong place to a better place, from a wrong area to a safe, peaceful, prosperous area. The definition of refugees here is more in line with *hijrah makkaniyah* in the sense of moving places or areas. The prohibition on repatriation under Islamic law is not limited to specific regions because Islam has no borders.

4. Restrictions on the Principle of Non-Refoulement

In Islam, several rules are not allowed to receive protection, especially from the state, namely:⁷⁶

1) Protecting perpetrators of non-political crimes, especially crimes that are subject to *had* (specific criminal sanctions), like intentional killing for no good reason; 2) Protecting perpetrators of crimes that violate international agreements; 3) Protecting refugees who are involved in serious crimes in their country of origin. Protecting oneself from persecution or soul loss is the main goal of protection. Thus, refugees should avoid serious crimes and seek asylum to avoid punishment. Contemporary international law and Islamic law share non-

⁷¹ Islamic Council of Europe, Universal Islamic Declaration of Human Rights (London: Islamic Council of Europe 1981) 19.

⁷² Organization of the Islamic Conference (OIC), ‘Cairo Declaration on Human Rights in Islam’ (5 Aug 1990) <<http://refworld.org/docid/3ae6b3822c.html>> accessed 8 April 2017.

⁷³ Dani Muhtada and others, ‘The Protection of Civil Rights for the Shi’ite Refugees of Sampang, East Java: A Systemic Governance Approach to Restore the Refugees’ Rights’ (2022) 12 (2) Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies 231, 249.

⁷⁴ Islamic Relief Worldwide (n 55).

⁷⁵ Ahsami Sami’un Jazuli (n 35) 13.

⁷⁶ Abu al-Wafa (n 54) 22.

refoulement exceptions. Refugees who pose a security risk will be exempt. Under Islamic law, actions that undermine Muslim faith and religion are the main grounds for denial of protection. Based on those explanations, it concludes that the principle of non-refoulement is a fundamental concept in international refugee law. It is primarily governed by the 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees and its 1967 Protocol. It serves as a cornerstone of refugee protection and ensures that individuals seeking asylum are not sent back to situations of danger or persecution. Non-refoulement is also widely recognised and accepted as a customary norm in international law, meaning that it is binding on all states, regardless of whether they are parties to the 1951 Convention.

Meanwhile, in Islamic law, the concept of non-refoulement aligns with several principles and teachings. While not explicitly mentioned as such, it reflects broader Islamic values and ethics. Islam places a high value on the preservation of human life, and there are numerous Qur'anic verses and Hadith emphasising the sanctity of life. The *hijrah* idea, typified by the migration of the Prophet Muhammad and his followers from Mecca to Medina in order to escape persecution, emphasises the significance of seeking a safe haven.

The link between the principle of non-refoulement in international law and Islamic law lies in their shared commitment to protecting individuals from harm and persecution. Both systems prioritise the safeguarding of human life, dignity, and freedom. Islamic law, through its principles of protection and sanctuary, aligns with the broader humanitarian objectives of international law, including the prohibition of refoulement. In this way, they complement each other in upholding the rights and safety of individuals facing persecution or danger. While international law provides a legal framework with specific provisions, Islamic law offers a moral and ethical foundation that emphasises compassion and empathy towards those in need. They contribute to a global framework for the protection of refugees and displaced individuals, bridging the gap between legal obligations and ethical responsibilities.

III. 'URF IN MUSLIM SOCIETY

In the context of the non-refoulement principle and its application within Muslim society, it is essential to explore the concept of '*urf*', encompassing its definition and prevalent practices among Muslim communities.

A. Definition and Term of 'Urf

The word '*urf*' is often interpreted as a custom, taken from the same root word as *ma'ruf* (kindness); the opposite is *munkar* (denier); therefore, '*urf*' means something good.⁷⁷ *Al-'urf* is something that is accepted by human nature and common sense.⁷⁸ In terms of terminology, the word '*urf*' is defined as the habit of the majority of the *ummah* (community) in judging a word or deed and is one of the arguments for establishing *Shariah* law. Linguistically, '*urf*' is defined as any habit carried out, whether good or bad.⁷⁹ *Ushul fiqh ulamas* (principles of jurisprudence scholars) distinguish the meaning of '*urf*' and custom in discussing its position as one of the arguments for establishing *Shariah* law.

⁷⁷ Zamakhsyari (n 45) 97.

⁷⁸ Rhesa Yogaswara, 'Al-'urf Sebagai Salah Satu Metode Ushul Fiqih Dalam Meng-Istimbath Setiap Permasalahan Dalam Kehidupan' (in Bahasa Indonesia) ['Al-'urf As One of the Ushul Fiqh Methods in Istimbath Every Problem in Life'] (2009) <<https://viewislam.wordpress.com/2009...>> accessed 26 March 2017.

⁷⁹ Ayman Shabana, *Custom in Islamic Law and Theory: The Development of the Concepts of 'Urf and 'Adah in the Islamic Legal Tradition* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan 2010) 194.

Qur'an gives three interpretations to the word *'urf* as:⁸⁰ 1) what is good and commendable; 2) what is known and accepted as good general practice; 3) what is known is important and necessary. On the other hand, the word *ma'ruf* is generally interpreted in the context of goodness and truth. All these verses interpret the words *'urf* and *ma'ruf* in a good way that is accepted by common sense and prevailing human habits.

The Hadith, which alludes to the meaning of *'urf*, is narrated by Imam Ahmad from Abdullah bin Mas'ud, which states:⁸¹

Zirr ibn Hubaysh reported: Abdullah ibn Mas'ud, may Allah be pleased with him, said, "Verily, Allah looked at the hearts of the servants, and He found that the heart of Muhammad, peace and blessings be upon him, was the best among them, so He chose him for Himself and He sent him with His message. Then, He looked at the hearts of His servants after Muhammad, and He found that the hearts of his companions were the best among them. Thus, He made them into the ministers of His Prophet, fighting for the sake of His religion. Whatever the Muslims view as good is good to Allah, and whatever they view as evil is evil to Allah."

The *ushul fiqh* experts used this Hadith as the basis that societal traditions that do not conflict with Islamic *shariah* principles can be used as a basis for consideration in establishing Islamic law.⁸² Ibn' Abidin gives the sense that *'urf* is something that has been entrenched, provisions are made repeatedly and received by logic in accordance with nature and a healthy mind.⁸³ When it is seen how the existence of *'urf* in the Islamic history, it would seem that the dimension of the Islamic history plays a role in the formation of law.

B. Types of 'Urf

Based on its scope, *'urf* can be divided into *'urf 'amm* and *'urf khass*.⁸⁴ *'urf amm* is a specific custom that applies widely throughout society and in all regions, while *'urf khass* is a custom that applies in certain areas and communities. *'urf 'amm* applies in all Muslim countries, from ancient times to the present. The scholars agree that *'urf 'amm* can be used as a source of law.

Regarding its object, *'urf* is divided into *'urf lafdzhi* (*'urf qauli*) and *'urf amali*.⁸⁵ *'urf lafdzhi* is a word whose meaning is understood in a certain society simultaneously, and there is no difference in the meaning. If this *'urf* applies in all Muslim countries or just a few areas, then it can be used as a source of law. As for *'urf amali* are actions that have become *'urf* and certain people carry out these habits. This *'urf* can also be used as a source of law, although it is not as strong as *'urf lafdzhi*.

⁸⁰ Qur'an, Al A'raf (the Heights) 7:199.

⁸¹ Hadith Musnad Ahmad, vol 1, book 379, hadith 3600.

⁸² Sulfan Wandu Sulfan Wandu, 'Eksistensi 'Urf dan Adat Kebiasaan Sebagai Dalil Fiqh' (in Bahasa Indonesia) ['The Existence of 'Urf and Customs as Proof of Fiqh'] (2018) 2 (1) Samarah: Jurnal Hukum Keluarga dan Hukum Islam 181, 183.

⁸³ Ansari Yamamah, 'The Existence of Al-Urf (Social Tradition) in Islamic Law Theory' (2016) 21 (12) IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science 43, 44.

⁸⁴ Zamakhsyari (n 45) 98.

⁸⁵ Andriyaldi Andriyaldi, 'Al-'Urf Theory and Its Relevance to Contemporary Jurisprudence Issues' (2021) 6 (2) Al Hurriyah: Jurnal Hukum Islam 118, 121.

As for *'urf shaheeh* and *'urf faseed* (*'urf bathil*), they are distinguished by their validity. *'urf shaheeh* is *'urf* that applies in society that does not conflict with the texts, does not eliminate benefits, and does not bring harm. Whereas *'urf faseed* or *bathil* is a habit contrary to the *Shariah* proposition and the basic rules in *Shariah*.

C. 'Urf As a Source of Islamic Law

The sources of Islamic law are divided into two groups: the primary and secondary sources. The primary sources are text-based, consisting of the Qur'an and Hadith. While secondary sources are based on opinion, namely *ijma'* (consensus), and *qiyas* (analogy). In addition, it is also known as the source of a sense of justice and custom (*'urf*). Islam pays excellent attention to traditions and conventions in society to be used as a source for Islamic law jurisprudence by perfecting and adapting to the limitations of the *Shariah*.⁸⁶ Before the Prophet Mohammad was appointed Rasulullah, customs (*'urf*) existed in the daily life of Arab society.⁸⁷ *Ushul fiqh ulamas* agree that *'urf*, which does not conflict with *Shariah*, can be used as a law source to establish *shariah* law. The Prophet adopted many of these habits. Islam did not immediately change Arab culture. Only *'urf* against Islamic principles is restricted.⁸⁸ Islamic law changes *'urf* concepts in Arab society to conform to Islamic teachings.⁸⁹

Based on this, it can be explained several forms of ratification of *'urf* as part of Islamic law, namely: a. *Ratification of 'urf through the Qur'an*: Many verses in the Qur'anic revelation, according to scholars, confirmed pre-existing social norms, i.e., the law of *qisas*, which is validated by the Qur'an, namely Surah Al-Maidah;⁹⁰ b. *Ratification of 'urf through the Hadith of the Prophet*: Ratification of the concept of *'urf* can be done apart from through the Qur'an, as the Prophet himself also ratified through several cases brought before him.⁹¹ An example is the case of Hind bint Utba;⁹² c. *Ratification through ijma' ulama*: It means that a decision, ruling, or legal interpretation in Islamic law is formally approved and considered valid based on the consensus of Islamic scholars. In other words, when a unanimous agreement (*ijma'*) among knowledgeable scholars is reached on a particular matter, it serves as a form of ratification, affirming the correctness and legitimacy of the decision or ruling. This consensus is a significant and respected aspect of Islamic legal tradition and adds weight to the legitimacy of a legal interpretation or judgment in Islamic jurisprudence.⁹³ For example, in the case of tax exemption for farmers who experience crop failure, this is the *'urf* of the Persian rulers.

⁸⁶ Waqar S. Ahmad Husaini, *Sistem Pembinaan Masyarakat Islam* (in Bahasa Indonesia) [*Islamic Community Development System*] (Bandung: Pustaka Perpustakaan Salman ITB 1983) 219.

⁸⁷ Fauziah, 'Konsep 'Uruf Dalam Pandangan Ulama Ushul Fiqh (Telaah Historis)' (in Bahasa Indonesia) ['The Concept of 'Uruf in the View of Usul Fiqh Scholars (Historical Study)'] (2014) 14 (2) Nurani 15, 17.

⁸⁸ Al-Dahlawi, *Wali Allah: Hujjah al-Balighah* (in Arabic) [*Wali Allah: His Eloquent Argument*] (Kairo: Dar al-Turas 1982) 1185.

⁸⁹ Muhammad S. El-Awa, *Punishment in Islamic Law* (Indianapolis: American Trust Publication 1982) 27.

⁹⁰ Al-Imam Al-'Alim Al-'Allamah Syamsuddin Abu Abdillah Muhammad, *Fathul Qorib* (in Arabic) [*Open the Closed*] (Kudus: Imron Abu Amar ed, I Ed. Menara Kudus 1982) 113.

⁹¹ H. A. Ghani, "'Urf -o-Adah (Custom and Usage) as a Source of Islamic Law' (2011) 1 (2) American International Journal of Contemporary Research 178, 180.

⁹² Muhammad Fuad Abdul Baqi, *Muttafaquun 'Alaih Shahih Bukhari Muslim: Himpunan Hadist Shahih Yang Disepakati Imam Bukhari Dan Imam Muslim* (in Bahasa Indonesia) [*Muttafaquun 'Alaih Sahih Bukhari Muslim: Collection of Sahih Hadiths Agreed on by Imam Bukhari and Imam Muslim*] Syahirul Alim al-Adib, Yasir Amri and Andi Wicaksono (eds) 1st edn (Beirut: Beirut Publishing 2015) 1889.

⁹³ Ahmad Mustofa al-Syalabi, *Ushul Fiqh Al-Islami* (in Arabic) [*The Islamic Jurisprudence*] (Beirut: Dar an-Nahdah al-Misriyyah, 1986) 21.

The conditions for an *'urf* to be used as a source of law in establishing *shariah* law are as follows: a. The *'urf* occurs in most cases in society, and its validity is adhered to by the majority of the community, b. The *'urf* does not conflict with what is clearly stated in the *Shariah* law, c. The *'urf* has been in effect in society before the problem to be determined by the law arises, d. The *'urf* will only be accepted if it does not conflict with *tashreeh* (one's firmness in stating something).

IV. THE PRINCIPLE OF NON-REFOULEMENT AS 'URF IN THE PRACTICE OF MUSLIM SOCIETY

Historically, Islam was the first to recognise the prohibition of repatriation for those who commit political crimes.⁹⁴ The prohibition of repatriation or non-refoulement is considered a principle originating from customary law (*'urf*). In the rules of Islamic Law, it is clear that something recognised as *'urf* is equivalent to a rule, or something agreed upon (*al-ma'ruf' urf-an ka al-masyrut syart'an*).⁹⁵ Likewise, something based on habit is equivalent to something written in the text or based on *Shariah* text (*al-tsabit bi al-'urf ka al-tsabit bi an-nass*).

Since *Rasulullah* founded the Islamic state in Medina, the prohibition on repatriation has been legal and applies to all refugees.⁹⁶ Envoys from the Quraysh of Mecca requested that the *muhâjirîn* be repatriated, but King Najasy refused. At that time, Ja'far bin Abi Talib, who was the spokesperson for the *muhâjirîn*, said, "*Kunna fi khairi dar wa akramu jiwâr*," which means that we are already in the best and noblest place in *jiwar*. This precedent in the case of migrating to Habeshah later became the basis of classical *fiqh* which stipulates that a *musta'min* or *mustajir*, even if he is a non-Muslim, may not be rejected and returned to his place of origin if the return endangers him, even though those who ask are people from his origin country, even his family.

The principle of non-refoulement is included in the concept of *hijrah*, which is accompanied by the Aqabah I and Aqabah II Agreements.⁹⁷ The principle of non-refoulement is familiar with the concept of *haqq al jiwâr* which was a custom of the Arabs before the advent of Islam. *Haqq al jiwâr* is a request for protection to someone who allows a public figure to express freely to protect someone so that other people may not harm these people as a tribute to the person protecting them. However, the concept of *Haqq al jiwâr* is closer to political asylum.⁹⁸

Returning or expelling refugees to places where violence and persecution are feared is opposed to Islamic principles known as the prohibition against breaking the assurance of protection or the principle of the prohibition against betraying the promise of safety for those who seek assistance. Under Islamic law, returning refugees to locations where they face a risk to their life or human rights is a treasonous act that has been deemed illegal.

During the second migration to Habeshah, another episode occurred that reflected the ban on return. The Quraysh at that time dispatched two chiefs to urge King Najasyi to evict the emigrants from their kingdom. The ambassador communicated the reasons for the Muslims'

⁹⁴ Mahmassani (n 40) 23.

⁹⁵ Abu al-Wafa (n 54) 23.

⁹⁶ Sidik (n 59) 50.

⁹⁷ Sharifah Nazneen Agha, 'The Ethics of Asylum in Early Muslim Society' (2008) 27 (2) Refugee Survey Quarterly 30, 33.

⁹⁸ Abu al-Wafa (n 54) 23.

reduced position. King Najassy chose not to evict or return the Muslims to the Quraysh after receiving information from the Muslims.

Based on the above, Islamic law protects refugees and asylum-seekers broadly and without discrimination. Because the asylum seeker trusted the Islamic State, violating non-refoulement is treason. According to *fiqh* experts, anyone who seeks asylum and enters the Islamic state without authorization shall be protected and not punished. The practice continues in modern international law. Arabs and Muslims assist refugees and asylum seekers as a noble custom.

V. CONCLUSION

The analysis in this article shows that there is the significant convergence between international law and Islamic law when it comes to the principle of non-refoulement. Both legal frameworks prioritise the protection of individuals from harm and persecution, emphasising the sanctity of life, dignity, and freedom. Moreover, it demonstrates that Muslim community considers non-refoulement to be an *'urf*. Non-refoulement prohibits expelling or denying people at risk of life, freedom, or dignity in their home country. Muslim society values humanity, justice, and solidarity. Islamic law seeks to defend life, freedom, and dignity regardless of race, religion, or origin. Viewing non-refoulement as a *'urf* in Muslim culture requires understanding Islamic religious ideals and how they promote human rights. By following non-refoulement and Islamic norms, Muslim communities can help the destitute.

This article suggests: 1) Muslims must learn about non-refoulement and be aware of it. Education and public campaigns with the help of religious institutions, community groups, and the media can get the word out about these principles and how they relate to religion and culture. 2) Muslim countries must have non-refoulement policies to protect refugees and immigrants and work with other countries to deal with the global refugee crisis; 3) Muslims must help refugees and immigrants fit in socially, economically, and culturally; 4) Recognizing and encouraging the synergy between international and Islamic non-refoulement law helps safeguard vulnerable people and promote a more compassionate and inclusive refugee response. States and communities can work together to protect refugees' rights and dignity in accordance with international and Islamic principles through aligning legal frameworks, raising awareness, and encouraging debate.